

Received 30.08.2023 | Accepted 09.09.2023 | Published: 13.09.2023 (online) | Subject Editor: Imre Fazekas
<https://doi.org/10.24386/LepHung.2023.19.2.53>
<https://zoobank.org/References/B889C884-3E86-4A4D-B6E0-047913DE660D>
<https://zenodo.org/>
<https://epa.oszk.hu/04100/04144>

Contribution to the knowledge of the Asiatic *Feliniopsis* Roepke, 1938, with the description of five new species from China (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, Xyleninae, Dypterygiini)

Péter Gyulai

Citation. Gyulai P. 2023: Contribution to the knowledge of the Asiatic *Feliniopsis* Roepke, 1938, with the description of five new species from China (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, Xyleninae, Dypterygiini). – *Lepidopterologica Hungarica* 19(2): 53–67.

Abstract. Description of five new species of *Feliniopsis* Roepke, 1938 from China, with 16 colour illustrations and 17 genitalia figures.

Keywords. China, new description, taxonomy

Author's address.

Péter Gyulai 3530 Miskolc, Mélyvölgy 13/A | Hungary | <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3878-2880>
E-mail: adriennegyulai@gmail.com

Introduction

A recent revision of the non-African *Feliniopsis* Roepke, 1938, by Kovács, G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay (2022), discusses more than 30 taxa, describing five new species and two new subspecies as well as establishing new synonymies, combinations and lectotype designations. At the start of the following year, descriptions of a further seven new species and one new subspecies of *Feliniopsis* was published, based upon a manuscript by the late Márton Hreblay (Bálint, Gyulai, Katona & Tóth 2023). The current study does not aim to clarify the identity of the taxa described in the two studies, but synonymy seems likely in some cases.

The author of this present paper examined a vast amount of *Feliniopsis* material from Asia, deposited in his private collection. The detailed study of the external features and the male and female genitalia structures of the collected specimens, and the comparison with the figures in the two above mentioned basic studies, led to the recognition of five species as new for science.

Unfortunately, most of the species are very local or rare, in several cases they are only known from a few specimens and it was possible to study a large series of only a few of them. Four of the newly discovered species are inhabitants in the montane forest regions of continental China, whilst one is a Chinese insular species.

It is worth mentioning that most of the taxa within this genus are very similar to each other in their external features (different shades of the brownish and brown-ochreous ground colour of forewings, and very uniform forewing pattern) and in male genitalia capsule configuration. The best keys for a positive determination of the males are in the construction of the ventral carinal bar of the aedeagus and in the shape of the vesica (number, arrangement and size of the diverticuli, cornuti, plates and scobination). In females, the shape of the antrum plate and the shape and lateral lobe or lobes of the ductus bursae are the most worthy of study.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein: HM = genitalia slide of Márton Hreblay in HNHM (Budapest, Hungary); HMB = collection of Márton Hreblay in HNHM (Budapest, Hungary); HNHM = Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary); GYP = genitalia slide of Péter Gyulai; KS = genitalia slide of Sándor T. Kovács; GRB = collection of Gábor Ronkay, Budapest; PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary); RL = genitalia slide of László Ronkay; m = male; f = female; HT = holotype; PT = paratype.

Description of new taxa

Feliniopsis guangxicola sp. n. (Figs 1, 2, 17, 27)

Holotype: male, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan, Jingxiu, 100 km SE of Liuzhou, 23°45' N; 109°45' E, 1200 m, 01 - 30. IV. 2005 leg. V. Siniaev & Team, slide no. GYP 5893 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Paratypes: 19 males, 9 females, with the same data (PGM); 9 males, 4 females, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan, Jingxiu, 100 km SE of Liuzhou, 23°45' N; 109°45' E, 1200 m, 15 - 30. III. 2005 leg. V. Siniaev & Team (PGM); 1 male, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan; Jingxiu; 24° 07' N; 110° 14' E 1700 m; 15 - 30. 11. 2006 leg. V. Siniaev & Team (PGM); 1 male, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan, Jingxiu, 100 km SE of Liuzhou, 23°45' N; 109°45' E, 1200 m, 1 - 31. VIII. 2005 leg. V. Siniaev & Team (PGM), slide nos.: GYP 5849, 5860, 5866, 5877, 5890 (males); GYP 5875, 5878, 5889, 5895 (females).

Diagnosis. The new species (Figs 1, 2) is a close relative of the insular Taiwanese *F. adrienneae* Kovács, G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay, 2022 (Figs 3, 4), and of the continental *F. distans* (Moore, 1882) (Fig. 8), *F. maiszae* Kovács, G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay (Figs 5, 6), and *F. manifesta* Hreblay, Katona & Tóth, 2023 (Fig. 7) (see the comment below on the taxonomic status of the latter two species). It most closely resembles *F. adrienneae*, from which it differs with the much darker brown (not reddish brown) wings, with slight dark ochreous-reddish-brown suffusion of the forewings, particularly in centre of the medial area; the regressed white colouration in the reniform stigmata and the wavy, stronger subterminal line. It is distinctive from *F. maiszae* and *F. manifesta*, being of larger size (wingspan 34–39 mm of the new species, 31–35 mm those of the two relatives); the darker brown (not reddish brown or ochreous-brown) ground colour, with slight ochreous-reddish-brown suffusion of the forewings in the centre, while the forewings of the two relative species have a much lighter and extended ochreous suffusion, particularly in the medial area. The new species outwardly is also reminiscent of *F. distans* (Fig. 8), from which it can be distinguished with the less elongate forewing, the simple postmedial line, which is more sinuous, broader in the first section, but less serrate in the further part, with only slight outer light brown shadow and the broader, wavy, subterminal line. The medial area of the forewing of *F. guangxicola* sp. n. is darker brown, with slight dark ochreous-reddish-brown colouration in the centre of the inner area of the forewings, whilst it is lighter, more or less pale ochreous in *F. distans*. The white definition of the reniform stigma with white dots in the outer part and outline of it is always present in the new species, while most of the specimens of *F. distans* do not have white colour in the reniform stigma which is, instead, filled with pale ochreous.

In the male genitalia, *F. guangxicola* sp. n. (Fig. 17), differs from the externally similar *F. adrienneae* (Fig. 18), mostly in the less robust, thicker, distally somewhat more curved and apically more acute harpe. In the aedeagus, the ventral carinal bar is shorter, but stronger sclerotized, more serrate-dentate, angled strongly at middle; the medial third is more angled inwards and the distal connection is stronger, but oval. The vesica subbasally is more ample, the medial lateral diverticulum is more prominent, having terminally a narrow sclerotized field of tiny cornuti, but lacking the small prominent second diverticulum; the subterminal diverticulum is smaller than in *F. adrienneae*. Additionally, there is a dentate plate in the medial part of the vesica in the new species, which is absent in *F. adrienneae*. *F. guangxicola* sp. n. can be distinguished from *F. maiszae* (Fig. 19), and *F. manifesta* (Fig. 20), by the shorter, distally less curved harpe; much smaller ventral valval lobe while the corona of *F. guangxicola* sp. n. covers a larger area and consists of shorter spines in the medial section than in its sister-species. The aedeagus of *F. guangxicola* sp. n. is broader than in the two relatives; the “ankle” is smaller, ventral carinal bar large, less strongly sclerotised and angled slightly (and not in a v-shaped, as it is in the two related species) at middle, but more serrate-dentate. The lateral medial diverticulum in the vesica is larger and stronger scobinate, while the subterminal one more scobinate. In comparison with *F. distans*, the differences are even more prominent. The harpe is less robust, thicker, distally somewhat more curved and apically more acute; the ventral valval lobe is shorter in the new species than in *F. distans*, whilst the corona of *F. guangxicola* sp. n. covers a

smaller area and consists of less spines than in its sister-species. The aedeagus of *F. guangxicola* **sp. n.** is broader than in *F. distans* (Fig. 21); ventral carinal bar is larger, less strongly sclerotized and angled slightly (and not in a v-shape, like in *F. distans*) at middle, but more serrate-dentate. The “ankle” of the carinal bar is more prominent in the new species than in its relative. The terminal part is less sclerotized, the distal connection is stronger, but oval, and not lenticiform. The vesica subbasally is more ample, the medial lateral diverticulum is more prominent, but smaller, having terminally a narrow sclerotized field of tiny cornuti, however lacks the small prominent second diverticulum; the subterminal diverticulum is significantly smaller, almost flat and not slipper-like.

In the female genitalia, the new species (Fig. 27), is distinct from the *F. adrienneae* (Fig. 28), in the following features: in *F. guangxicola* **sp. n.** the antrum plate is not symmetrical (unlike in *F. adrienneae*), anteriorly more dilated, and the lateral margins are not parallel and the posterior section of ductus bursae is evenly broad, straight and tubular. The junction of ductus bursae to corpus bursae is much longer, the medial-lateral lobe less prominent, but much elongated and larger, and the corpus bursae is more elongated-saccate than in *F. adrienneae*. In comparison to the other three congeners (Figs 29, 30), the most conspicuous differences are in the posterior section of ductus bursae, which is evenly broad, straight and tubular in the new species. The posterior section of ductus bursae is evenly broad, straight and tubular, whilst it is posteriorly dilated in the close relatives; the junction of ductus bursae to corpus bursae is much longer, straight, and the medial-lateral lobe less prominent, but much elongate and larger than in the close relatives. Additionally, the new species lacks the two small lateral outgrowths, which are present in *F. maiszae* (Fig. 29).

Description. (Figs 1, 2). Medium-sized species, with the wingspan 33–39 mm. Antennae filiform in both sexes. Head and thorax hazel-brown, forewings brown with hazel-brown and pale ochreous-brown suffusion, the lightest near the outer edge of the reniform stigmata. The outer half of the wing generally paler coloured than the inner half. Antemedial and postmedial lines double, dark brown filled with paler brown; dark dots and triangles visible at the initials of the crosslines subterminal line fine, pale ochreous, with dark arrowheads at inner side. Orbicular stigma small, elliptic-ovoid shaped, pale brown; reniform stigma large, elliptical, more or less filled with white colouration in the outer part, while the inner part brownish. Claviform stigma large, conspicuous, more or less quadrangular, dark brown. Cilia as ground colour, with paler intervals at veins. Hindwing unicolorous brown, with obscure darker discal spot and medial line. Underside of the wings brown, reddish suffused along the forewing costa, and light ochre in the inner part of the hindwing. The ghost of the postmedial line in the forewing and of the discal spot and medial line in the hindwing dark brown, conspicuous.

Male genitalia (Fig. 17). Uncus strong, long, distally flattened, apically hooked. Upper section of tegumen narrow, curved inwards at upper part; juxta small, triangular, weakly sclerotized, with strong medial prominence between transtillae; vinculum rather short, V-shaped. Valva strong, medially slightly constricted, distally dilated; cucullus with finely rounded apex and strong, broad corona. Distal ventral lobe of valva not elongate, ventrally rounded, evenly crescent-shaped. Harpe strong, broad at base, distally tapering and finely curved dorsad subterminally; evenly tapering terminally and pointed apically. Aedeagus broad, ventral carinal bar large, sclerotized, with a slight “ankle” basally; medial third only slightly angled inwards at middle, serrate-dentate at length; the distal third is in a slight connection with an oval sclerotized bar. Vesica broadly tubular, curved dorsad, a dentate plate situated in the medial part. The lateral medial diverticulum prominent, having terminally a narrow-sclerotized field of tiny cornuti, while the subterminal one much smaller, flattening, scobinate.

Female genitalia (Fig. 27). Ovipositor conical, papillae anales elongated, apically finely rounded. Apophyses posteriores medium-long, apophyses anteriores much shorter. Antrum more or less quadrangular, anteriorly somewhat dilated, thus the lateral margins not parallel. The posterior section of ductus bursae evenly broad, straight and tubular; the junction of the longitudinally strongly ribbed ductus bursae to corpus bursae long, anterior two-third broadened, with elongate, medially prominent, medial-lateral lobe; corpus bursae elongated-saccate.

Comment. The taxonomic status of the *F. maiszae* and *F. manifesta* is debatable, since both have been described from a single male and the external and the male genitalia features almost

overlap; subspecific classification is possible. For the correct decision, a larger number of specimens of both sexes and the study of their genitalia would be necessary. A short series from Nepal was found with the same locality and date, from which two dissected males have been identified as likely the second species. The single female from there with the same data and external features is treated as the same taxa.

Biology and distribution. The new species is known only from prov. Guangxi, China, where it seems to be not rare.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to the Chinese province from which the entire type series originates.

***Feliniopsis multidiverticulata* sp. n.** (Figs 9, 10, 22)

Holotype. China, Jiangxi, Wuyi Shan, Xipaihe village, 1500 m. 27° 54' N, 117° 20' E, 01-31. 10. 2005 leg. V. Sinaiev & Team, slide no. GYP 5850 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Paratypes. 1 male, China, Jiangxi, Wuyi Shan, Xipaihe village, 1500 m. 27° 54' N, 117° 20' E, 01-30. 11. 2005 leg. V. Sinaiev & Team (PGM); 2 males, China, Guangxi, Yuecheng Ling, 750 m. 26° 18' N, 110° 59' E, 12-15. 12. 2007 leg. V. Sinaiev & Team (PGM), slide nos: GYP 5854, 5861, 5897 (males).

Diagnosis. The new species (Figs 9, 10) outwardly resembles the continental *F. guangxicola* sp. n. (Figs 1, 2) (see above) and the Taiwanese *F. adrienneae* (Figs 3, 4), but in the genital organ it shows very different, unique features that are missing in the other Asiatic species of the genus. The new species is mostly larger than the two congeners (wingspan 37-40 mm, compared with 32-39 mm in *F. adrienneae*, 33-39 mm in *F. guangxicola* sp. n.). It can be distinguished by the more elongate, much lighter, more varied forewings, with more extensive pale ochreous and ochreous-brown suffusion, without reddish-brown shade and the more tortuous and serrate postmedian line, particularly in its middle and lower section.

In the male genitalia, *F. multidiverticulata* sp. n. (Fig. 22) differs from the two closely related species (Figs 17, 18) in the longer, evenly slimmer valva with shorter corona; stronger juxta and transtillae; v-shaped vinculum; additionally from *F. adrienneae* the new species has a less robust, thicker, distally falciform and more acute harpe. In the aedeagus, the ventral carinal bar is without an "ankle" and is much shorter than in the two relatives, bearing a small lateral, strongly sclerotized, double apex. The vesica is very distinctive from the other congeners, having a strongly sclerotized, dentate, longitudinal plate and six diverticuli, from which 3 and 4 are strongly scobinate, while at the basal of 5 an oval scobinate patch is visible. The female is unknown.

Description. Medium-sized species, with the wingspan 37-40 mm. Antennae filiform in males. Head and thorax pale hazel-brown; forewings varied with extensive pale ochreous and ochreous-brown suffusion, the lightest near the outer edge of the reniform stigmata. Antemedial and postmedial lines double, the postmedial line tortuous and serrate, particularly in its middle and lower section; subterminal line fine, pale ochreous, with dark arrowheads at inner side; dark dots and triangles at the initials of the crosslines visible. Orbicular stigma small, elliptic-ovoid shaped, pale ochre-brown; reniform stigma large, angular with white dots at the corners, more or less filled with white colouration in the outer part, while the inner part pale brownish. Claviform stigma large, conspicuous, more or less quadrangular, dark brown. Cilia as ground colour, with paler intervals at veins. Hindwing unicolorous brown, with obscure darker discal spot and medial line. Underside of forewings pale brown, but reddish suffused along forewing costa, and pale, light ochre in the hindwing. Ghost of the postmedial and subterminal lines in the forewing and of the discal spot and of the medial line in the hindwing dark brown, conspicuous.

Male genitalia (Fig. 22). Uncus long, slim, distally broadly flattened, apically hooked. Upper section of tegumen narrower, curved inwards at upper part; juxta small, triangular, strongly sclerotized, as the two with medial prominence between transtillae; vinculum rather short, u-shaped. Valva strong, elongate, almost evenly slim; cucullus with rounded apex and strong corona; distal ventral lobe of valva not prominent and elongate, ventrally rounded, evenly crescent-like. Harpe strong, broad at base, distally tapering and finely falciform distally; evenly tapering terminally and pointed apically. Aedeagus broad, straight, ventral carinal bar fine, sclerotized,

bearing a small lateral, strongly sclerotized, double apex. The vesica is unique in the genus, having a strongly sclerotized, dentate, longitudinal plate and six diverticula, from which 3 and 4 are strongly scobinate, while at the base of 5 an oval scobinate patch is visible.

The female is unknown.

Biology and distribution. The new species is known from the provinces Guangxi and Jiangxi of China. It seems to be a late autumn and early winter species.

Etymology. The name of the new species is after its unique vesica configuration.

***Feliniopsis fuscofusa* sp. n.** (Figs 11, 12, 23, 31)

Holotype. male, China, Sichuan, Volong Reserve, Siguliang Shan, 31° 09' N, 103° 20' E, 1. XI. - 31. XII. 2004, leg. V. Siniaev & Team, slide no. GYP 5856 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Paratype. one female, China, Sichuan, Volong Reserve, Siguliang Shan, 31° 09' N, 103° 20' E, 1. 30. IV. 2006, leg. V. Siniaev & Team (PGM), slide no. GYP 5862 (female).

Diagnosis. The new species (Figs 11, 12) is most similar to the insular Taiwanese *F. rubrofusa* Fu, Ronkay, Ronkay & Wu, 2013 (Fig. 13), but is very different both in the male and female genitalia. The new species is much larger than *F. rubrofusa* (wingspan 38-41 mm, compared with 30-32 in *F. rubrofusa*), with larger Noctuidae maculation, without white colouration in the pale ochre-brown orbicular stigma, regressed whitish (not white as in the related species) colouration in the outer part of the reniform stigma and the more tortuous and serrate postmedian line, especially in its middle and lower section. In the male genitalia, *F. fuscofusa* sp. n. (Fig. 23), is similar to *F. multidiverticulata* sp. n. (Figs 9, 10, 22) (see above), from which it differs in the following external features: the forewing of the new species is much darker, less variegated, almost monochromatic, with varying shades of dark brown without ochreous suffusion, the apex less elongate; the postmedial line is obscure and perpendicular toward the inner costa; the medial line on the underside of the hindwing is not sinuous.

In the male genitalia *F. fuscofusa* sp. n. (Fig. 23) is not a close relative of the externally similar *F. rubrofusa* (Fig. 24), but is closer to *F. multidiverticulata* sp. n. (Fig. 22), (see above), from which it can be separated by the shorter, distally evenly broaden valva with dorsally broader corona; v-shaped vinculum; more robust, distally less falciform, subterminally-terminally stronger but less acute harpe and somewhat longer ventral lobe of valva. In the aedeagus, the ventral carinal bar is longer and more prominent than in related species, The vesica is more ample in *F. fuscofusa* sp. n. than in *F. multidiverticulata* sp. n., the strongly sclerotized, dentate, medial plate is much shorter, diverticulum 3 is only weakly scobinate; the subterminal-terminal section is densely diverticulate and bears two, parallel, falcate elongate scobinate bars, with tiny cornuti, which are absent in *F. multidiverticulata* sp. n. In the female genitalia, the new species (Fig. 31), is distinctive from that of *F. rubrofusa*, (Fig. 33), due to the longer ovipositor with acute papillae anales; higher, funnel-like antrum plate; much longer ductus bursae and much smaller, medio-lateral lobe. No female is known of *F. multidiverticulata* sp. n..

Description. Medium-sized species, with the wingspan 36–40 mm. Antennae filiform in both sexes. Head and thorax brown, with slight greyish on the head. Forewing almost monochromatic, with varying shades of dark brown colour without ochreous suffusion, the darkest in the medial and terminal parts; the apex not elongate. Antemedial and postmedial lines double, the postmedial line obscure, tortuous and serrate, and perpendicular toward the inner costa. Subterminal line fine, ochreous, with long, black arrowheads at inner side. Orbicular stigma pale ochre-brown, without white colouration. Reniform stigma elliptic-angular shaped, with a weak whitish patch in the outer part, while the inner part pale brownish; terminated outside with three-five white dots. Claviform stigma large, conspicuous, more or less quadrangular, dark brown. Cilia as ground colour, with paler intervals at veins. Hindwing unicolorous brown, with obscure darker discal spot and medial line, cilia ochreous. Underside of forewings dark brown, lighter suffused along forewing costa, brownish-ochreous in the marginal field; ghost of postmedial line brown, that of the subterminal line ochreous. Hindwing light ochreous brown, with strong brown shade of the discal spot, of the medial line and of the pale subterminal line.

Male genitalia (fig. 23). Uncus long, distally broadly flattened, apically hooked. Upper section of tegumen narrower, curved inwards at upper part; juxta small, strongly sclerotized, with medial prominence between transtillae; vinculum rather short, v-shaped. Valva strong, elongate, almost evenly slim; cucullus with slightly rounded apex and strong corona; distal ventral lobe of valva not prominent, but elongate, ventrally rounded, unevenly crescent-shaped. Harpe strong, broad at base, distally evenly weaker and slightly falciform; evenly tapering terminally and pointed apically. Aedeagus broad, straight, ventral carinal bar fine, sclerotized, bearing a small lateral, strongly sclerotized, pointed apex. Vesica ample, the medial plate rather short, strongly, dentate, diverticulum 3 is only weakly scobinate and bears two, parallel, falcate elongate bars. The subterminal-terminal section is densely diverticulated; bears two, parallel, falcate elongate scobinate bars, with tiny cornuti; the terminal diverticulum strongly scobinated.

Female genitalia. (Fig. 31). Ovipositor conical, papillae anales elongate, apically acute. Apophyses posteriores long, slim, apophyses anteriores much shorter and broader. Antrum plate high, funnel-like, strongly and evenly sclerotized, posteriorly with a very small medial prominence. The posterior section of ductus bursae is short, evenly broad, straight and tubular, partly covered with a small, sclerotized, subquadrangular appendage. The long and longitudinally strongly ribbed-sclerotized, asymmetrically broaden ductus bursae to corpus bursae have an elongate, medially prominent, medio-lateral lobe, while on the opposite lateral side a larger (anteriorly) and a smaller (posteriorly), broadly rounded extension. Appendix bursae long, terminally angular. Corpus bursae elongated-saccate.

Biology and distribution. The new species is known only from Sichuan province.

Etymology. The name of the new species is after its ground colour.

***Feliniopsis tsinlinga* sp. n.** (Figs 14, 32)

Holotype. female, China, prov. Shaanxi, Tsinling Mts., Fopin Mt., 33° 35' N, 108° 01' E, 1800 m.; 01–31. VIII. 2005, leg. V. Siniaev, slide no. GYP 5857 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Diagnosis. The new species (Fig. 14), is the northern sister species of *F. fuscofusa* sp. n. (Figs 11, 12), (see above). It differs from *F. fuscofusa* sp. n. in the slightly smaller size (wingspan 37 mm, compared with 38–41 mm in *F. fuscofusa* sp. n.), less elongate forewing apex, much extended white colouration in the outer part of the reniform stigma and the broader and lighter shadow of the postmedial line. It is much larger than the externally similar, but not close relative *F. rubrofusa* (Fig. 13), (wingspan 37 mm, whilst 30–32 of *F. rubrofusa*) with larger Noctuidae maculation, without white colouration in the pale ochre-brown orbicular stigma, and have more serrate postmedial line, especially in its middle and lower section, with a much broader and lighter shadow of it. In spite of the strong resemblance to *F. fuscofusa* sp. n. in the external appearance, in the female genitalia the new species is very distinctive from that of *F. fuscofusa* sp. n., mainly in the following features: the new species has longer antrum plate, which posteriorly ends straight, lacking the medial slight prominence; the medial-lateral lobe of ductus bursae is much larger; the ductus bursae is strongly asymmetric, curved, lacks the two lateral extensions, much wider in the middle, and weaker posteriorly than in the *F. fuscofusa* sp. n.; the appendix bursae is much smaller, terminally rounded and not angular as in the close relative species. The new species cannot be confused with that of *F. rubrofusa*, due to the longer ovipositor with acute papillae anales; higher, funnel-like antrum plate; much longer, asymmetrically curved ductus bursae with less prominent medial-lateral lobe.

Description. Medium-sized species, with a wingspan of 37 mm. Antennae filiform in the female. Head and thorax brown, with slight greyish on the head. Forewing of the new species almost monochromatic, with varying shades of brown colour without ochreous suffusion; the apex not elongate. Antemedial and postmedial lines double, the postmedial line tortuous and serrate, having a broad lighter shadow. Subterminal line fine, ochreous, with long, black arrowheads at inner side. Orbicular stigma brown, without white colouration, encircled with a fine yellowish line. Reniform stigma angular shaped, with a conspicuous whitish patch in the outer part, while the inner part pale brownish, surrounded outside with five white dots. Claviform stigma large, conspicuous, more or less quadrangular, dark brown. Cilia as ground colour, with

paler intervals at veins. Hindwing brown, lighter in the basal part, with obscure darker discal spot and diffuse medial and subterminal lines, cilia ochreous. Underside of forewings dark brown, lighter suffused along forewing costa, brownish-ochreous in the marginal field; ghost of postmedial line brown, that of the subterminal line ochreous. Hindwing whitish with slight brown suffusion, with strong brown shadow of the discal spot, of the medial line and of the pale subterminal line.

Female genitalia. (Fig. 14). Ovipositor conical, papillae anales elongate, apically acute. Apophyses posteriores long, slim, apophyses anteriores much shorter and broader. Antrum plate funnel-like, strongly and evenly sclerotized. The posterior section of ductus bursae is short, evenly tapering, connected with a small, sclerotized, subquadrangular appendage. The long, asymmetrically broadened, curved and longitudinally strongly ribbed-sclerotized, ductus bursae to corpus bursae with an elongate, medial-lateral lobe. Appendix bursae small, terminally rounded. Corpus bursae elongated-saccate.

Biology and distribution. The new species is known only from Shaanxi province.

Etymology. The name of the new species is after its type locality.

Feliniopsis hainana sp. n. (Figs 15, 25)

Holotype. male, China, prov. Hainan, 1-30. IV. 2003, leg. local collector, slide no. GYP 5824 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Diagnosis. *F. hainana* sp. n. (Fig. 15), is the sister species of *F. indistans* (Guenée, 1852) (Fig. 16). The single male specimen of the new species is rather worn, therefore a detailed comparison with the closely related *F. indistans* is not possible. However it is easily visible that the reniform stigma of the new species has a slightly slanted 8-shape, while in the related species it is variegated; furthermore *F. hainana* sp. n. has a higher, rather cube-shaped, claviform stigma, while it is weaker and less angular in *F. indistans*. In the underside of forewings, the new species has a conspicuous arched, broad long streak, starting from the basal and evenly tapering toward the inner costa; while it is paler, almost straight and much weaker in *F. indistans*.

In the male genitalia configuration, *F. hainana* sp. n. (Fig. 25), differs from *F. indistans* (Fig. 26), in the slightly shorter, but distally much stronger uncus; larger juxta; terminally more elongate valva with smaller corona with lesser cornuti and longer harpe. In the aedeagus, the ventral carinal bar is significantly stronger and more prominent than in the relative species, armed a very strongly sclerotized long plate, with three large and some short cornuti, whilst it is slight in *F. indistans* with two or three tiny cornuti and a small scobinate field in its end. The vesica is more ample in *F. hainana* sp. n. than in *F. indistans*; the medial cornutus much larger, an elongate-deltoid plate. The vesica is much more prominent medial-laterally in the new species, with four strongly sclerotized plates, well separated from the extension of the ventral carinal plate; while there are only two smaller ones, conjoined with the extension of the ventral carinal plate, ended in a slightly scobinate diverticulum in *F. indistans*. The terminal diverticulum is tongue-like, conspicuously larger than in *F. indistans*. Female is unknown.

Description. Medium-sized species, with a wingspan of 32 mm. Antennae filiform. Head and thorax brown, with slight greyish on the head. The single male specimen of the new species is rather worn, therefore not all elements of the wing pattern are clearly visible. Forewing of the new species triangular, apex not elongate. Ground colour almost monochromatic, with varying shades of brown without ochreous suffusion. Crosslines fine, brown, the postmedial line tortuous-wavy, the medial line lies close to its inner side and parallel to it. Subterminal line fine, ochreous, with a few black arrowheads at inner side. Orbicular stigma elongate, pale ochre-brown; reniform stigma also, having a slightly slanted 8 shape. Claviform stigma large, conspicuous, quadrangular, dark brown, rather cube-shaped. Hindwing unicolorous pale brown, the marginal area somewhat darker; discal spot darker, arched. Underside of the forewings pale brown, with an arched, broad long streak, starting from the basal and evenly tapering toward the inner costa. Hindwing whitish, with slight ghost of the discal spot and of the medial line.

Male genitalia (Fig. 15). Uncus long, distal section evenly broader, apically hooked. Upper section of tegumen narrow, curved inwards at upper part; juxta small, strongly sclerotized, with medial prominence between transtillae; vinculum rather short, u-shaped. Valva strong, terminal-

ly elongate; cucullus with slightly rounded apex and short corona with a field of strong cornuti. Distal ventral lobe of valva elongate, ventrally rounded, unevenly crescent-shaped. Harpe strong, broad at base, distally evenly weaker and slightly curved; evenly tapering terminally and pointed apically. In the aedeagus, the ventral carinal bar strong, armed with a very strongly sclerotized long plate, with three large and some short cornuti. Vesica ample, medially-laterally prominent; the medial cornutus large, an elongate-deltoid plate. The vesica bears four strongly sclerotized conjoined plates, well separated from the extension of the ventral carinal plate. Terminal diverticulum tongue-like, conspicuously large. Female is unknown.

Biology and distribution. The new species is known only from the island of Hainan in China.

Etymology. The name of the new species is after its occurrence.

Acknowledgements. The author is grateful to Sándor T. Kovács (Szeged, Hungary) for consultation and for the photo documentation of *F. adrienneae*. Thanks are due to Judit Heck, the widow of Dr Márton Hreblay, for the access of the material kept in the Hreblay collection, and to the staff of the Lepidoptera collection of the Hungarian Natural History Museum for the documentation of the Hreblay Lepidoptera specimens and microscopic slides, and were taken by B. Tóth (HNHM, Budapest, Hungary) (the photos are the property of the HNHM). Also, much thanks to Adrienne Gyulai-Garai (Miskolc, Hungary) for greatly helping with the computer work; to Imre Fazekas (Pannon Institute, Pécs, Hungary) for the publication of the manuscript. Comments on the final manuscript, as well as additional linguistic tuning, were made by Colin W. Plant (Great Britain); the author also expresses his grateful thanks to him.

Text fig. 1. Outline of the geographical locations of the new species (see text for details). (Graphic based on Google Maps. Made by Imre Fazekas).

Figures 1–8. *Feliniopsis* spp. adults. 1. *F. guangxicola* **sp. n.**, HT, m, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan, GYP 5893 (PGM); 2. *F. guangxicola* **sp. n.**, PT, f, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan, GYP 5878 (PGM); 3. *F. adrienneae* PT, m, Taiwan, Ilan county, KS 193 (HNHM); 4. *F. adrienneae* PT, f, Taiwan, Ilan county (GRB); 5. *F. maiszae* Kovács, G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay, 2022, m, Nepal, Kanchenjunga, Surke Danda (PGM); 6. *F. maiszae* Kovács, G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay, 2022, f, Nepal, Kanchenjunga, Surke Danda, GYP 5894 (PGM); 7. *F. manifesta* Hreblay, Katona & Tóth, 2023, HT, m, Thailand, Changwat Nan, HM 11210 (HMB) 8. *F. distans* (Moore, 1882) Nepal, HM 11542 (HMB).

Figures 9–16. *Feliniopsis* spp. adults. 9. *F. multidiverticulata* **sp. n.**, HT, m, China, Jiangxi, GYP 5850 (PGM); 10. *F. multidiverticulata* **sp. n.**, PT, m, China, Jiangxi, GYP 5854 (PGM); 11. *F. fuscofusa* **sp. n.**, HT, m, China, Sichuan, GYP 5856 (PGM); 12. *F. fuscofusa* **sp. n.**, PT, f, China, Sichuan, GYP 5862 (PGM); 13. *F. rubrofusa* Fu, Ronkay, Ronkay & Wu, 2013, PT, m, Taiwan, Kao Hsiung (PGM); 14. *F. tsinlinga* **sp. n.**, HT, f, China, Shaanxi, Tsinling Mts., GYP 5857 (PGM); 15. *F. hainana* **sp. n.**, HT, m, China, Hainan, GYP 5824 (PGM); 16. *F. indistans* (Guenée, 1852), m, China, Yunnan, GYP 5853 (PGM).

Figures 17–20. *Feliniopsis* spp. male genitalia. 17. *F. guangxicola* **sp. n.**, HT, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan, GYP 5893 (PGM); 18. *F. adrienneae* PT, m, Taiwan, Ilan county, KS 193 (HNHM); 19. *F. maiszae* Kovács, G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay, 2022, Nepal, Kanchenjunga, Surke Danda, GYP 5888 (PGM); 20. *F. manifesta* Hreblay, Katona & Tóth, 2023, HT, m, Thailand, Changwat Nan, HM 11210 (HMB).

Figures 21–24. *Feliniopsis* spp. male genitalia. 21. *F. distans* (Moore, 1882), Nepal, Langtang, KST 183 (HMB); 22. *F. multidiverticulata* sp. n., HT, m, China, Jiangxi, GYP 5850 (PGM); 23. *F. fuscofusa* sp. n., HT, m, China, Sichuan, GYP 5856 (PGM); 24. *F. rubrofusa* Fu, Ronkay, Ronkay & Wu, 2013, PT, m, Taiwan, Nantou county, RL. 10752 (HNHM).

Figures 25–26. *Feliniopsis* spp. male genitalia. 25. *F. hainana* **sp. n.**, HT, m, China, Hainan, GYP 5824 (PGM); 26. *F. indistans* (Guenée, 1852), m, China, Yunnan, GYP 5853 (PGM).

Figures 27–28. *Feliniopsis* spp. female genitalia. 27. *F. guangxicola* **sp. n.**, PT, China, Guangxi, Dayao Shan, GYP 5878 (PGM); 28. *F. adrienneae* PT, Taiwan, Ilan county, RL12338 (GRB);

Figures 29–33. *Feliniopsis* spp. female genitalia. 29. *F. maiszae* Kovács, G. Ronkay & L. Ronkay, 2022, Nepal, Kanchenjunga, Surke Danda, GYP 5894 (PGM); 30. *F. distans* (Moore, 1882), Nepal, HM 11542 (HMB); 31. *F. fuscofusa* **sp. n.**, PT, China, Sichuan, Volong res., GYP 5862 (PGM); 32. *F. tsinlinga* **sp. n.**, HT, China, Shaanxi, Tsinling Mts., GYP 5857 (PGM); 33. *F. rubrofusa* Fu, Ronkay, Ronkay & Wu, 2013, PT, Taiwan, Nantou county, RL. 10922 (HNHM).

References

- Bálint Zs., Gyulai P., Katona G., & Tóth B. 2023: New species and genera described by Dr. Márton Hreblay (1963–2000) in his monograph on North-Thailand noctuid moths (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). – *Annales Musei Historico-naturalis Hungarici*, 115: 17–199.
- Kovács S.T., Ronkay G. & Ronkay L. 2022: The Asiatic species of the genus *Feliniopsis* Roepke, 1938 (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, Xyleninae, Dypterygiini). – *Fibigeriana Supplement Book Series of Taxonomy and Faunistics*, Heterocera Press Volume 3, Budapest, 2022, pp. 211–240.